

Marginalization in Iran a threat to the social Security of cities

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Abstract

Usually marginalized are known people living in cities, but due to the set of factors they have been unable to absorb in the system of economy, society, and as a citizen of the facilities and municipal services benefit. However, today's the margins are known as the part of the city which have common tissue with the cities, the margins have often infertile Culture and remain crime-prone areas, and become problematic. Where, according to sociologists, cultural and regional poverty and crime is the main feature of this culture and the crime is born from this culture, not only is a threat to social security of the people of this region, but also the Social security of city's residents threatens. Social Security, is a multi-dimensions issue which studying that in marginalized areas needs of studying in various fields of social science and behavioral research, For this purpose, this subject have been tried in this sweeping of these areas is discussed wholly.

Keywords: social security, marginalization, social control, participation, anti-social behavior.

Introduction:

Marginalization is considered as an urban problem, and the main source of delinquency and crime. It seems that people who live in marginalized areas are separated from structure of public policy and power and considered as groups of social posts. Statistics show that the majority of crime and social harm is related to marginalized neighborhoods in the cities. Social Security has a lower coefficient (Athari, 1996, 14). Now the question arises, what factors cause severe social damage being marginalized communities?

Spatial forms and physical environment of the neighborhood provides for the occurrence of crime and social processes and culture of marginalized or other events and factors are involved? Due to social tissue, cultural, economic of marginalized areas the variety of crime are found and social security is so low. Because the most important characteristic of marginalized areas, is the occurrence of crime and so the threat of social security.

Figure (1) conceptual model of the research, authors, 2013

Statement of Problem:

Over the past five decades, the regional development policy has led to a rapid and significant change. Regional development strategies, has created the various developments in the field of new economic geography in recent years that globalization theory has challenged, (Khammar and et al, 2012, 20). However, today's the margins are known as the part of the city which have common tissue with the cities, the margins have often infertile Culture and remain crime-prone areas, and become problematic. Where, according to sociologists, cultural and regional poverty and crime is the main feature of this culture and the crime is born from this culture, not only is a threat to social security of the people of this region, but also the Social security of city's residents threatens. Not only threat is among its residents, but also raised concerns about the city's residents. It threatens the social security and considering of the growth of the marginalized and fading the boarder between cities and margins one hand and increasing murder and crime in these areas, on the other hand, the question arises: First, what factors make the incidence of crime in these areas and Ultimately being lower of social security is involved. Secondly, what ways must be taken which lead to omit the marginalized areas and raising the social security index. On the other hand the growing marginalization in Iran, especially in big cities is considered a serious threat to social security. In these areas the lack of social control, easily the types of crime are seen which all of these elements cause that social security are threatened. Slum area residents in areas of poverty, lack of educational opportunities and studies generally cultural poor, developing talents and abilities of people prevents.

Framework marginalization

In the Amid's Culture the "margin" means beside everything and innuendo from those of the others. The term marginalization with interpretations as settled informal settlements and slums self-created is almost synonymous. Marginalization or informal settlements is one of the most prominent figures of urban poverty, within or bordering towns (especially in big cities), in form of self-created look like without a permit of building, a formal application with the urban poor and low-income segments of the cumulative quantity and quality of life formed town (Piran, 2003, 9).

Marshall Klynard believes that the border, has its own culture and this culture is a way of life. The types of traditional livelihoods (subsistence) of the marginalized is transferred from generation to next generation and usually have a culture of its own. Culture reflects the lifestyle of lower social marginalization that is usually known as the culture of poverty (Naghdi, 2004, 9).

Robert Park who is one of the Chicago School experts, believes that Slum area man, is a kind of personalities that creatures in a place and a time which is produced in resulted of conflicting of races, cultures, societies and people new To the area. The fate which makes such people will be condemned to live in a time of two separate worlds, is the same fate, that makes them in relationship with the worlds in which they live, makes them accept the role of foreign and a man's world. John Turner, optimistic and positive theory adopted in 1969, and described marginalization as a suitable solution to the housing problem in urban areas of developing countries (the same).

On the other hand Stone Cast from psychological view the marginalization mental phenomena and the resulting economic and cultural struggle of the lower classes of society, called the main heart of society. He says: individual human being Slum area, through migration, education, marriage and social or cultural factors that belongs to a group of social or cultural - without a satisfactory adjustment to the other - leaves his groups and find himself at the side and margin of both, but it is not member of any. When fighting groups of individuals as a private matter of experiences this person will be a member of Slum area. Charles Abrams in 1964 illustrated marginalization as the process of capturing urban areas to the housing and to the power of law and the law of power explicated.

Marginalized and alternative titles

Extent marginalization phenomenon around the world and many different cultures and literatures scientific of societies have caused information on various topics to be used for marginalization. The nominal number of academic titles and names can be divided into two parts interactively (locally) can be classified as:

Phenomenon of marginalization of academic topics while explaining the above phenomena are common features to the different ways. From different areas of morphology (morphology) of such areas is considered. These terms are as follows:

- 1 - informal houses
- 2- houses of low-income
- 3 - Semi-permanent houses
- 4 - mats Fallen
- 5 - spontaneous human settlements
- 6- unplanned human settlements
- 7 - marginal human settlements
- 8 -houses self-made

In Iran, marginal human settlements according to their morphology, physical and social qualities that arose from geographical and cultural situation in various cities it has several names. Such as shack, slum, room, Ghamir, Gorgin, Kpary wall, Pashly land without fences and helpless, underground burial chamber, tin and ... (Ahmadian, 2004).

Social security and regional balance:

Attention to social security in different areas of social is essential and some of scientists and government consider it as more important and to variety countries each of them try to meet their social security. Due to the Social security has a high correlation with other aspects and factors in the development, maintaining of life, political survival of national government and countries, and it also provides the introduction of many important processes it is interesting and important. One of the most important factors that may threaten a community's social security is a regional inequality in different geographic regions of the country. Regional Justice means that all geographic regions of the country have a same accessibility and opportunities of development and welfare, education, health and... Same level, Or at least there are not considerable and significant differences between regions and provinces; Because inequalities gradually inspire deprived people who live in areas of marginal geographic region and the sense and the view of that the central government is incapable to establish justice "comprehensive" in different areas of society :and due to unfavorable geographical and climatic conditions in remote areas, it costs lower per capita of the public

resources. As a result of this dichotomy in the marginalized individuals and rich central provinces which have the level of better development; Marginalized populations will eventually be led to loss of loyalty, and make an appearance of unrest and discontent, in long-term make a danger of "divergence" and "social insecurity" in society. What the above was mentioned is true about the city and suburban context, because if there is no regional balance between context and margins, and the margins are always spent in poverty, discrimination and injustice will also be exhibited. So, Insecurity in the border towns would be normal. Because of lack of facilities, education and livelihood opportunities due to lack of proper distribution is that a quite conducive environment will be provided for a variety of social harm. Creating regional balance in the area can make a governing of security in marginalized areas (Masoudi Far, 2009, 5).

The reason of tendency toward some anti-social behavior and social maladjustment in marginalized areas

It can be said that the tendency towards anti-social behavior in individuals, or at least the potential for this area, there are in the residents of these areas. The purpose of tendency toward antisocial behavior is a kind of mental readiness to disobey social rules and feelings of hostility towards the environment. The results of done researches indicate that the trend to antisocial behavior is now influenced by factors such as, individual anomic status, education level, political satisfaction, effectiveness authorities and individuals in solving problems.

High population density, low education levels and the type of predominant of income, and most marginalized, can be a factor of encouraging to create social disorder. History of towns, residential complexes and migrants to the area, which indicates that these places are without a social identity - independent culture, so in these areas there are not any sponsors to maintain the values and norms, and from each areas is moved to these points there is a less social and cultural resistance. Marginalized who are victims of social ostracism are frequently against all principles and social norms (Safavi, 2003, 2). Social and class conflict, especially marginalized young children of these lower class urban rather than urban middle class, in the most severe its form cause forming of subcultures of deviant and delinquent youth. These delinquent subcultures are usually mannish with murder and act to pillage, vandalistic behavior, drug abuse, theft, street violence, criminal groups working with adults, prostitution and break the law. And occasionally in line their goals they use their class young women. Often, the police's and community group's behavior is a kind of manners that leads to institutionalize and deepening of these social conflicts, and while sociological studies indicate a series of maintain solutions to this problem in operating of social absorbing policies (Mohseni, 2001, 15).

The law escaping and break the law as a value among urban youth marginalized families and individuals tied to the social rate of success. This is partly because of the inability of economic and social weakness of marginalized, can be analyzed. So that the social and economic development and promoting from the common law considers impossible. Lack of educational and economic facilities causes marginal youth which have very low level of skill and knowledge in order to achieve

a decent job, even with a low income can not afford. There is a culture of poverty and the poverty of the region, causing abnormal behavior and ultimately reduce the crookedness of social security in marginalized areas, which subsequently caused the unsafe environment that crimes such as murder, robbery, drug and alcohol producing. .. The result is (agha bakhshi, 2004, 18).

Marginal Settlements and spread of crime and social other pathway may be related to the following factors will influence:

Social control and social security in marginalized areas:

Oversees of all aspects of society can be considered the most important factors of social security in the marginalized areas, In fact, by controlling social is that social security will be established in these areas. But social control in marginalized areas involve damages that needs to be examined the basic categories:

A person learns by being socially acceptable patterns of behavior in various situations, what is the difference between competent and incompetent behavior patterns? Social control in fact is the development process of socialization. This surveillance refers to the ways and means that are applied in society that cause people to adapt themselves to the expectations of a particular group or community. If social surveillance is applied properly, person's behavior becomes behavior consistent with the expected behavior (Rafi-Pour, 2000). Not important and the limited means of social surveillance forces in marginalized areas have always been the main causes of antisocial behavior.

Although marginalized areas can be a safe environment for those who are considered as an abnormal and deviant behavior when they do their deviant behavior, Because, as it was pointed out in these areas of social control is very poor and unsafe environment for residents who are threatened with suffering from different directions. In fact, formal and informal mechanisms of social supervision in marginalized areas due to function poorly, marginalized areas have created a safe environment.

It should be known that the process of social disorganization comes from of conflict norms and values , cultural change, cultural gaps and weaknesses of primary relationships. Therefore, these reduction of external social control and are pushing people towards deviant behaviors. In fact, features such as urbanization, mobility, location, Marginal Settlements, ethnic or racial heterogeneity and rupture of the family, all together prevent the ability of community to exert social control over the population. The sequence of this followed, in marginalized areas, deviant behavior, and space away from the eyes of the law will be prepared for any kind of injury and crime. In fact, lack of social organization, lack of social order and finally social aberrations can occur in the absence of social control.

Pathological Migration, Marginal Settlements and Social Security

Research done on the relationship between Marginal Settlements and social deviations indicate that there is a positive relationship between the two is associated with high rates of spatial mobility. It is sufficient to point out that the effect of immigration on population growth between 1980 and 1985 in nine of the 27 countries of the Asia-Pacific region, most of the countries have urban natural growth. In a study on Tehran, Isfahan, and Karaj

are done; the major periods of population increase in these cities are as follows:

- 1 - Tehran from 1319 to 1355 - an average of 94/6% per year.
- 2-Karaj from 1345 to 1375 an average of 1/10% per year.
- 3 - Isfahan from 1335 to 1365, an average of 6/4% per year (Zanjani and Moghaddam 2003).

The reducing of population growth rate in some big cities - in the case of immigrants to settle in the cities dues to be low levels –it causes an intense spontaneous increase of the rural population, especially in rural settlements near the large cities and the marginalized, as planned, the impress of migration on the population of metropolitan cities are not the same. If in the report projects population growth as a result of natural growth of the fifth-largest city was 91%. Due to this large volume of migrants in these cities has been not predicted so marginalization in them has developed. In fact, the more immigration and less urban facilities in cities where are acceptable Immigration the negative consequences of immigration is higher (Abdullahi, 2003, 11). According to the above description should be considered in the informal settlements and marginalized immigrants are in the fact reasons such urban attractions, the facilities available in the city and ... Have migrated into urban and suburban areas stay.

The migration in terms of cultural impact that is having on the social security in these areas will be threatened. Because immigrants are inhabited from different cultures and different ideas and believes in these regions, this multiplicity of tastes and believes will cause damages in the various fields:

Community participation and empowerment of the marginalized in the society for sustainable security

Many communities have achieved to this point to reach the desirable community to develop a program to provide better development, public participation should be emphasized first. In other words, to achieve any kind of active participation of people in social fields are required.

Marginalized in the realm of economic life, to live in community and social systems, but they are integrated into in the community and therefore will not be accepted as official citizens. These separation of urban society, with features such as texture, housing, job skills and social characteristics make them distinguish from civilians (Hadizadeh, 2004, 11). Emphasis on social relations and distinguishing them is important because depending on the mode of interaction of social and marginalized people, is usually distinguished from the principles of urban against pressures vulnerable to recommended. Moreover, illiteracy, armed with the lack of specific migration, and economic ties to the city's inability to attend and join in the result of persistent unemployment, distortion and damage to their fields, providing more formal citizens. So, in the author's view the best model for public participation in Marginal Settlements, is model reconstruction, and new social engineering to empower residents. Such a model, which simply provides planning and makes decision from down to the local and regional approach emphasizes and other programs are not dictated from the top to the residents of the area. in the another model, the second step is to attract participation of people, preserve the dignity of local residents, to point this belief that people

are potential capability, however, they are living in the marginal areas. Thus making them susceptible to local public affairs, and public awareness of the possibility of improving the quality of life of local development plans, it is the residents and their presence adds to the confidence.

Thus making them susceptible to local public affairs, and the possibility of improving the quality of life and then making public awareness local development plans which is the right of residents and their active presence increase their confidence. Because until the people of the region do not feel the necessity a problem correctly they will not intervene in the practical activities. According to the above description, an important step in the direction of social participation and social security is considered among marginalized areas, because of this way somehow first comprehensive social supervision be implemented secondly to implement programs and policies in the field of sustainable security through appropriate steps will be taken :

"Community participation, empowerment and sustainable security"

Conclusion:

Marginal Settlements as an agent who knows all the economic areas of the city are living in urban but not absorbed, marginal settlements in developing countries refers to slums around large cities and caused many of the residents these area have failed to attract the socio - economic cities urban, and the facilities and services use. And generally marginalized areas rather than urban facilities nor have the look and villages. One of the major problems the marginalization has created for big cities is a threat of their security. Statistics show that most crimes happened in Tehran was done by people who live in the margins. Overall structure of marginal areas so that they can participate in the activities of mafia cliques operating groups and their abnormal. Also, the statistics show that 3 out of every murder that takes place in the Tehran, two cases occur in people marginalized. The majority of crimes and offenses including robbery, drug sales, prostitution, violence, conflict, and ... in the region is that the examples could be mentioned such as Pakdasht catastrophes, murders Mashhad spider, Khak Sefid etc. Lack of employment, poor working conditions and lack of reward and consequently the lack of fixed income for living, low education, high fertility, makes marginalized people lives for himself and his family turned to antisocial behavior. having no economical meeting and social insecurity, such as lack of adequate housing and proper nutrition and medical facilities, human relations leads to weakness and the weakness of human relationships, in turn, leads to abuse and neglect of other people. If people's basic needs are met, rebellion, rape and commit crimes lower will be followed. Major elements of the crime because of poverty, but not the main reason. certainly the root of all crime, and ultimately threaten of social security genera is in poverty and social underdevelopment of the organization. Without the proper planning and policy making in the this area will naturally insecure and marginalized areas of cities will increase these security context.

The roots of crime and anti-social behavior within the text should be cured for the same crime. And these need for a comprehensive study in the social, urban development and needs.

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